

Democratising the sublime: spectacular danger and the rise of mass leisure by the sea

In his autobiographical novel *Kiddar's Luck*, Jack Common chronicles his experiences of growing up in early twentieth-century Tyneside, offering an intimate portrait of working-class life in North East England. Among his recollections are outings with friends, taken on foot from the city of Newcastle to the nearby coast, journeys that traversed landscapes shaped by industry, leisure and social change. The trip would take him and his companions through the industrial hinterland of the region:

On our left the dark caverns of a series of engineering works puffed oil fumes at us; on our right, the destructor chimney occasionally fanned down its foul smoke; even the oncoming air had the rattle of riveting guns from the shipyards in it.¹

The industrial vista extends beyond mere landscape into the lungs, the sensorium, into the very texture of experience. It is a structuring force, an inscription of labour onto the young bodies that move through this terrain. This infernal vision, emblematic of the heavily industrialised North East of the time, stands in stark contrast to the landscape of the coast. As Common and his companions draw closer to the ocean, the oppressive industrial milieu recedes, giving way to a markedly different environment:

the air was full of the great sea glow, a salt radiance brightened all the long Tynemouth streets. And at the end of them, the land fell off at the cliff edge into a great shimmering nothingness immense all ways over the lazy crimping of seas on their level floor.²

Here, space is no longer disciplined by the mechanised rhythms of industry but is instead subsumed into an elemental vastness, where solid ground gives way to an ephemeral play of light and motion. If the city's industrial periphery marks a zone of confinement – of labour, fumes, and relentless noise – then this coastal threshold presents its dialectical counterpoint: an opening into the unbounded, where perception itself is unmoored amid the immensity of air, light, and sea. It is the vanishing point of civilisation, where the regimented world of work and habitation dissolves into a shimmering, elemental void.

If Common's words present a fairly archetypal description of the English seaside resort – as a pastoral, a natural landscape other to the dirt, noise and smoke which constituted the experience of industrial modernity – this is a vision which finds greater resonance in the nineteenth century than the twentieth. By the latter era, the British seaside was characterised

¹ Jack Common, *Kiddar's Luck* (Bath: Cedric Chivers, 1971), 112. The motif of escape is clear in his subsequent remark: 'and yet we had the whole length of the river to walk before we were clear of industrialism.'

² *Ibid.*

by its own idiosyncratic modernity – albeit one dedicated to leisure, rather than labour. Indeed, Common goes on in his narrative to relate that the trip to the coast invariably included a visit to the Spanish City, an extensive fairground in the coastal town of Whitley Bay. Common fixtures of English seaside resorts, fairgrounds offered visitors a kaleidoscope of mechanical rides and phantasmagorical spectacles. These attractions, with their dizzying sights, cacophonous sounds, and disorienting sensations, in fact mirrored the rapid, disorienting and fragmentary character of modern urban experience.

At first glance, Whitley Bay appears to provide a fairly typical example of the British seaside resort, with relatively genteel beginnings giving way to a boom in the first half of the twentieth century as leisure became more widely accessible to the working class, resulting in a vast expansion of tourist infrastructure.³ Looking at the visual and textual archive of the town, mainly from the early twentieth century, this article traces the discursive development of Whitley Bay from a semi-rural idyll seen as other to the shocks and experiences of urban modernity, to a busy resort popular with the local working-class labour force, employed in the factories, shipyards and coal mines of the area.⁴

In many respects, Whitley Bay developed along the model of Blackpool, the exemplary northern working-class resort, and the location of the first permanent seaside fairground in the country. Indeed, although on a smaller scale, this perceived similarity is frequently remarked upon in the literature. Yet Whitley Bay is not simply a derivative copy. It offers its own idiosyncratic contribution to a historiography that has hitherto relegated the town to a passing mention. Indeed, the heavy scholarly investment in a handful of overdetermined sites – particularly Blackpool, and to a lesser extent Brighton – has contributed to a degree of historiographical oversight, obscuring other, smaller resorts with their own distinctive trajectories.

Whitley Bay's specific conditions render it uniquely significant. While major resorts like Blackpool and Brighton developed more gradually through the nineteenth century, Whitley Bay's emergence was comparatively sudden. In 1911, it ranked only as the twenty-fifth largest seaside resort in the country by population, yet it had seen the third most rapid rate of growth over the preceding three decades.⁵ It was the only major resort on the northeast coast, a region marked by a substantial working-class population, while also undergoing simultaneous

³ As G. R. Searle has noted, "by 1911, such had been the recent improvement in living standards, some 55 per cent of the population were making day trips to the seaside, while another 20 per cent were booking holiday accommodation there". G. R. Searle, *A New England? Peace and War, 1886-1918* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004), 554.

⁴ Originally called just Whitley, the "Bay" was added to the town's name in 1902.

⁵ John K. Walton, *The English Seaside Resort: A Social History, 1750-1914* (Leicester: Leicester University Press, 1983), 65; 68.

development as a dormitory town for a growing middle-class commuter base. In this sense, Whitley Bay can be seen as a microcosm of broader social, cultural and economic changes reshaping Britain at the turn of the century.

This article pays particular attention to how representations of the town and its visitors were framed in the context of these shifts. While firsthand working-class accounts like Common's are unfortunately scarce, sources such as guidebooks, newspapers, advertisements, and literature offer a rich archive for analysis. These are normative texts – bourgeois imaginaries, articulating hegemonic fantasies of a naturalised social order at the seaside – and as such, they provide a valuable lens through which to explore how the imaginative valences attached to the sea shaped the discourses of mass tourism. The coastline, in these texts, emerges not simply as a physical space but as a culturally saturated site, where classed visions of leisure, morality, and pleasure were projected and contested.

Much attention has been paid to the historical transitions undergone by the cultural and social attitudes which help define our understanding and conceptualisation of the seaside as a site of leisure. Alain Corbin, in his seminal study *The Lure of the Sea*, traces the emergence of the popular fascination with the coast as a site for the bourgeois pursuit of health and leisure, which saw the coastal landscape reimagined as a space of aesthetic pleasure – a natural landscape characterised above all by its wild sublimity – rather than purely one of peril or economic utility.⁶ Corbin's account, however, stops short of the rise of mass coastal tourism due to its temporal range ending in 1840. More specifically, the British seaside resort is something of an overdetermined site within scholarly traditions concerned with working-class identity, leisure, and mass entertainment (particularly cultural studies, and to an extent, social history). This focus is often framed by an exploration of "popular" or "low" culture, which has historically been tied to working-class experience. The seaside resort thus became a critical space for examining how notions of culture, class, and consumption converge, providing insight into the dynamics of modern leisure and the social functions of mass entertainment.

John Urry's influential study *The Tourist Gaze* dedicates its second chapter to the British seaside resort as a key site in the development of modern, mass tourism. In this context, the seaside becomes one of the first terrains on which tourism, as a form of cultural consumption, becomes shaped by a distinctly optical mode of engagement: landscapes are packaged into spectacles, reconstituted as increasingly unreal views to be consumed by a passive gaze. By the twentieth century, Urry argues, "everyone had become entitled to the pleasures of the 'tourist gaze' by the seaside", signalling both a democratisation of leisure and

⁶ Alain Corbin, *The Lure of the Sea* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1994).

new forms of social control.⁷ This reading fits within a persistent historiographical narrative in which the British seaside undergoes a shift from a natural site of bourgeois health and retreat to a space of mass proletarian leisure. Furthermore, the latter stage has been characterised by a focus on culture as a site of working class resistance, and particularly with the concept of the Bakhtinian carnivalesque as the lens with which to engage it. Rob Shields, for instance, traces at Brighton a passage into the twentieth century whereby a “medicalised, liminal beach and the sublime of the late Victorian middle class” was displaced by the beach’s “carnivalisation”.⁸ Tony Bennett offers an analysis of Blackpool, which while a departure from Shields’ reading, retains its Bakhtinian emphasis, tracing the repression and disappearance of traditional, carnivalesque pursuits, to be replaced by the hegemonic forms of cultural control manifested in the town’s idiosyncratic modernity.⁹ Again focusing on Blackpool, Darren Webb takes issue with both Shields and Bennett’s readings, denying that the seaside ever offered an authentic experience of Bakhtinian carnival, arguing instead for a continued understanding of the resort as an affirmative (and distinctly modern) site of utopian working-class leisure experience.¹⁰

However, the search for Bakhtin (or his absence) amid the exuberant crowds of the holiday beach has proven misleading, occluding other potential readings. Beneath the dialectic of carnival and control lies a deeper elision – the elemental, affective force of the sea itself. Specifically, this historiography has little to say regarding the relationship between the earlier emphasis on the natural, sublime aspects of the maritime landscape, and later developments of the seaside as a place of mass leisure, characterised particularly by the immersive kinaesthetic experience of funfairs and the wild excesses of the proletarian crowd. Representative is Adrian Franklin’s sentiment that the fairground was fundamentally “detached from the sea and the beach, and the rituals of health and restfulness that they grew from”.¹¹ Yet, as I will argue, it is precisely in this disjunction that the cultural work of the seaside might be more productively read: the transition from therapeutic to thrilling, from horizon to helter-skelter, is not simply a historical break, the transition from a romantic escape from the modern to its hedonistic embrace. Rather, it presents a reconstitution of the sublime within modernity’s logic: a re-scripting of the body’s encounter with wildness. The funfair’s detachment from the sea signals not rupture, but a rechanneling of affect.

⁷ John Urry, *The Tourist Gaze* (London: Sage, 2002), 44.

⁸ Rob Shields, *Places on the Margin: Alternative Geographies of Modernity* (London: Routledge, 1991), 111.

⁹ Tony Bennett, ‘Hegemony, Ideology, Pleasure: Blackpool,’ in *Popular Culture and Social Relations*, ed. T. Bennett, C. Mercer, and J. Woollacott (Milton Keynes and Philadelphia: Open University Press, 1986). See also Tony Bennett, ‘A Thousand and One Troubles: Blackpool Pleasure Beach,’ in *Formations of Pleasure*, ed. T. Bennett et al. (London: Routledge, 1983).

¹⁰ Darren Webb, ‘Bakhtin at the seaside: Utopia, modernity and the carnivalesque,’ *Theory, Culture and Society* 22:3 (2005), 121-38.

¹¹ Adrian Franklin, *City Life* (London: Sage Publications, 2010), 181.

This article, in its investigation of the considerable continuities in this narrative, offers a cultural history of the seaside as a space where the sublime is democratised. Unlike the sublime of the romantic imagination – where awe was encountered through solitary contemplation – the seaside invites participation, often chaotic and communal. Attending to the continuity of the sublime allows for a reappraisal of longstanding debates that have animated cultural readings of the seaside—particularly the tension between the seaside as a space of hedonistic release and as a site of authentic, potentially subversive, cultural expression. Rather than resolving this binary, viewing the seaside through the enduring lens of the sublime reframes the conversation altogether: it shifts focus to the deeper structuring impulses that persist beneath the surface, across transformations in leisure, class politics, and spatial aesthetics.

The Pastoral Imaginary: The seaside as natural cure and edifying spectacle

Previous to its emergence as a popular tourist destination, some of the earliest published references to Whitley Bay appear in nineteenth-century journals of amateur natural history and geology, as a place among whose cliffs, beaches and rock pools one could search for examples of the fossils, flora and fauna to be found there.¹² As Alain Corbin has argued, refined leisure pursuits like these reflected a pastoral vision of the coast as a natural haven seen not merely as an escape, but as a romantic antidote to the evils of the modern world.¹³ Indeed, such characterisations fed into early touristic discourses concerning the town. The *Illustrated Guide to Whitley Bay* of 1907, one of the first of such guides, claims that “those who are indigenious to conditions where health is daily sacrificed to money-making are the most anxious about the [...] circumstances of a watering place”.¹⁴ Like many seaside resorts with their origins in the nineteenth century, fresh air, salt water bathing and serenity were the first attractions which drew tourists to Whitley Bay from the area’s urban centres. Strikingly, in its eagerness to promote the rejuvenating powers of nature, the guide seems possessed of a sensitivity to the deleterious conditions of labour under modern capitalism, boasting that in the town “the death rate seldom exceeds ten to eleven per thousand; and that in spite of the number of organically

¹² See, for instance, Natural History Society of Northumberland, Durham, and Newcastle-upon-Tyne, *Natural history transactions of Northumberland and Durham: Volume 1* (London: Williams & Norgate, 1867), 182.

¹³ Corbin, *Lure of the Sea*, 62.

¹⁴ J. George Gibson, *Illustrated Guide to Whitley Bay* (North Shields: W. J. Potts, 1907), 12.

weak subjects who sleep here the year round while working in one of the busier town centres nearby”.¹⁵

This conception of the seaside as the remedy to the ills of modern industrial society was embedded in pseudo-scientific claims regarding the curative powers of nature. “For those who can endure it,” the guide claims, “it is in the highest degree conducive to health to bask upon the weed strewn rocks while the clear shining of the sun is releasing ozone from the drying vegetation”. Of course, in order to receive the full benefits of the sea’s health-giving properties, it was necessary to literally immerse oneself in it. “The sharp bite of the saline waters at Whitley Bay is of the utmost value in all cases of debility, and especially to the jaded business man, in setting up a pleasant and energising re-action in the whole body”.¹⁶ This prescription of the sea as a curative force reflects a broader biopolitical logic in which the regulation of bodies – exhausted, disciplined, and rendered docile by modern labour – manifests the bourgeois imagination of nature as a site of controlled revitalisation. Here, leisure is framed within the logic of economic utility: restoration not for its own sake, but as a means to return, reconstituted, to the rhythms of work.

Alain Corbin suggests that the “strategy for seaside holidays was to enjoy the sea and experience the terror it inspired”.¹⁷ Indeed, it was not only the sea’s invigorating, calming influence which characterised its representation as a natural space. The sea was also seen as a wild, untameable, dangerous force of nature. It was against this backdrop that the American artist Winslow Homer made his 1881 visit to Cullercoats, a fishing village bordering Whitley Bay. The images he produced of the local landscape and people during his stay portray a world in which nature and humanity were pitted against one another; where the sea, whilst providing a livelihood, was also a source of danger and destruction. Many of Homer’s Cullercoats paintings focus on the local women, who played a significant role in the local maritime economy, highlighting their resilience and connection to the sea. In works like *Perils of the Sea* and *Watching the Tempest* – the titles alone underpin Homer’s preoccupation with the spectatorship of maritime catastrophe – women are pictured working, caring for children, but overwhelmingly engaged in watching, waiting, gazing out to sea for the return of their male counterparts.

These fisher folk, who he renders possessed of a hardiness which betrays their constant labour in the face of the harsh elements, seem at once in conflict with nature, and a part of it. According to Helen Cooper, they “seemed to Homer indivisible from nature and, hence,

¹⁵ Ibid., 18.

¹⁶ Ibid., 23.

¹⁷ Corbin, *Lure of the Sea*, 62.

became his connection to nature's power".¹⁸ In October 1881 Homer was to encounter the full destructive intensity of this power as an eye witness to one of the frequent shipwrecks on the coast, and the subsequent rescue of the sailing vessel's crew by the local lifesaving organisation. Having made sketches of the scene as it unfolded, Homer depicted the rescue operation in his large canvas *The Wreck of the Iron Crown*, again portraying heroic coastal populations pitted against a sublime nature which threatens to overwhelm them.

Homer's pastoral seaside vision was in fact a reactionary one: while depicting the simplicity of a people apparently untouched by the corrupting influence of modernity, it had little place for the steam trawlers which were coming into common use in the area at that time, yet remain generally absent from his paintings.¹⁹ Furthermore, the already extensive infrastructure of modern bourgeois leisure is distinctly absent from Homer's rough, wild seascape – we get no impression from his paintings that the immense pleasure palace, the Tynemouth Aquarium and Winter Garden, which had opened in 1878, only three years before his arrival, looked out over the same seascapes he depicted.

As well as its aquarium and winter garden, this huge structure of brick and glass housed pleasure grounds, card and billiard rooms, reading and smoking rooms, promenades and a refreshment bar. Opened by Member of Parliament for Tynemouth and North Shields Thomas Eustace Smith, the MP's speech emphasised that this monument to bourgeois leisure was intended "to promote the increase of knowledge, to promote innocent and healthy recreation, and to give pleasure to the community at large".²⁰ The language reflects the Victorian era's pervasive belief in the moral and physical enrichment that could be achieved through structured, edifying leisure activities. The emphasis on "innocent" and "healthy" pursuits further reveals anxieties about urban degeneration and the perceived need to contain leisure within morally acceptable boundaries. The building thus serves as a microcosm of Victorian efforts to democratise access to cultural enrichment while subtly reinforcing social norms.

In the staged promenade of the winter garden, we glimpse the phantasmagoria of class relations in late Victorian leisure. An article from the British society magazine *Vanity Fair* announcing the building's opening imagines the harmonious scene which might unfold there. The setting is one of controlled spectacle:

In the gay autumn days the inquiring pitman and his expensively-attired spouse will wander on the breezy terrace. They will make wondering researches into the

¹⁸ Helen A. Cooper, *Winslow Homer Watercolours* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1986), 92.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 95.

²⁰ 'The Tynemouth Aquarium,' *Lords and Commons: A Reprint of Eight Hundred Speeches and Two Hundred Letters, etc., Volume I* (London: J. Hall, 1878), 173.

habits and customs of lobsters, and their pleasant burr will attract the attentive tourist. The genteel traveller from Newcastle will be able to thread his way amid the natives without having his sensibility shocked, for the miner, though simple enough, is never vulgar.²¹

The passage operates within a discursive regime that seeks to classify, regulate, and aestheticise social difference. The miner and his wife are not merely visitors to the winter garden but subjects under observation, reduced to objects of curiosity within this orchestrated theatre of social order. This reflects a broader ideology of the late nineteenth century, in which industrial workers were increasingly incorporated into national cultural narratives, not as autonomous subjects but as quaint, comprehensible figures whose presence could be reconciled with bourgeois sensibilities. Furthermore, the discursive parallel between the spectacle of maritime nature and the proletariat at leisure provides a crucial insight into how bourgeois narratives would go on to frame working class leisure at the seaside, as it would go on to develop into the next century.

Shipwreck with Spectators: The seaside as theatre of the sublime

The discordant juxtaposition hinted at by the coexistence of Homer's shipwreck and the pleasure palace, of the sea's archaic wrath and the carefree frivolity of seaside leisure, is made manifest in an 1897 photograph of the wreck of the sailing vessel *Luna* on Whitley sands (Figure 1). Upon close inspection, near the wrecked vessel, several mobile bathing huts can be seen along the beach. To the left of the scene, near the base of the cliffs, a large marquee tent rises – perhaps for refreshments or performances. Adjacent to this are the faint outlines of fairground rides, a nod to the burgeoning development of seaside entertainment. These attractions frame the scene with a juxtaposition of natural drama and human amusement: where shipwrecks and storms once stirred awe and fear, they now coexisted in uncanny simultaneity with the trappings of modern entertainment.

This photograph strikingly stages what Michael Taussig has described as the Benjaminian “Dialectical Image” of the seashore, the “rupture into modernity of the archaic as ‘second nature’”. “The beach,” Taussig writes, “is the ultimate fantasy space where nature and carnival blend as prehistory in the dialectical image of modernity”.²² The shipwreck, an event that belongs to a more ancient, perilous relationship between humanity and the sea, now plays

²¹ ‘Tynemouth,’ *Vanity Fair*, September 7, 1878, 124.

²² Michael Taussig, ‘The Beach (A Fantasy),’ *Critical Inquiry* 26:2 (2000), 248-78: 258.

out against the incongruous backdrop of the Victorian seaside, a space increasingly codified by bourgeois recreation. Yet it also renders visible the sea's refusal to be tamed, an echo of an older order of danger and ruin that modernity cannot fully repress. The figures in the photograph are both witnesses and participants in the transformation of the shore into a theatre of disaster, their presence turning the scene into something at once sublime and banal. Images of the wreck were even sold as postcards, commodifying nature's chaos for leisurely consumption.

This notion of shipwreck as tourist spectacle is manifested in a contemporaneous newspaper article reporting the 1891 wreck of the steamer *Gothenburg City*: "The news of the occurrence soon reached Whitley and neighbouring villages and there were soon large crowds present [...] with a view to obtaining a view of the distressed vessel."²³ Drawn to the drama of destruction, crowds gathered on the shore to witness the sublime terror of human fragility against the sea's indifferent force. The same newspaper reports the ongoing fascination with the spectacle of the wreck the following day, noting the steady flow of onlookers drawn to the scene:

She is a fine steamer of about 8000 tons burthen and her unpleasant predicament has made the island & its vicinity quite a place of pilgrimage for the visitors at Whitley, Cullercoats and Tynemouth. A good many boats from Tynemouth and Whitley arrived during the evening and quite a brisk trade was driven in ferrying the curious to the vessel-some rowing round it and others going on board.²⁴

The arrival of the crowds signals a shift in the cultural terrain of the sublime. No longer confined to the privileged reflections of the painter or the philosopher, it is performed collectively, encountered viscerally. This is the sublime as experience rather than contemplation, where awe is not a matter of intellectual reflection but an immediate, embodied response. The boats, ferrying people out to the wreck, transform it into a site of participation, as if the sublime must be approached, encircled, even touched. Yet there is something transactional in this encounter. The very act of witnessing becomes structured by access, by movement, by payment, a sublime that is no longer purely an aesthetic or philosophical category, but a consumable experience.

This logic of sublime tourism found fertile ground in Whitley Bay, a landscape defined by its extensive cliffs and sweeping beaches, offering the ideal vantage point for observing the ocean at its most tempestuous. A 1910 tourist guide captures the magnetic allure of such natural drama, emphasising its grip on the popular imagination:

²³ 'Steamer Aground Near Whitley,' *Shields Daily News*, June 28, 1891, 3.

²⁴ 'Steamer Ashore Near St. Mary's Island,' *Shields Daily News*, June 29, 1891, 3.

In time of storm the table rocks are seen at their best, the sight of the angry sea churning itself to fury at the base of the rocks and casting its mighty billows against this immovable barrier, only to be broken up into foam and spray and cast harmlessly over the promenade above is indeed enchanting. Hundreds of visitors come to Whitley Bay to visit these rocks in time of storm.²⁵

This passage reflects the modern seaside's transformation into a theatre of the sublime, where nature's most volatile expressions are framed as safe, consumable spectacle. It encapsulates the paradox at the heart of the coastal imaginary: the promise of danger tamed, of an elemental force brought within the bounds of leisure. This interplay between turbulence and containment recalls John Urry's notion of the tourist gaze, in which landscapes are structured not merely to be observed but to provide a curated experience – one that simultaneously evokes awe and neutralises threat. As Urry observes, the nineteenth century “saw the emergence of “scenic tourism” and a much more private and passionate experience of beauty and the sublime”.²⁶ However, as the guide notes, by the early twentieth century, with the democratisation of leisure such experiences were becoming available to “hundreds” of people at a time.

In 1867 Charles Dickens visited the North East in the course of a national speaking tour. A keen walker, Dickens was characterised by Walter Benjamin as the archetype of the urban stroller, the “man who roams the big city lost in thought”.²⁷ In a letter, Dickens relates a trip to Tynemouth to walk by the sea, an “escape” from the “heavy atmosphere” of the city. As he discovers, however, at the seaside such flaneurial pursuits could be incompatible with the wild unpredictability of the sea:

There was a high wind blowing, and a magnificent sea running. Large vessels were being towed in and out over the stormy bar with prodigious waves breaking on; and, spanning the restless uproar of the waters, was a quiet rainbow of transcendent beauty. The scene was quite wonderful. We were in the full enjoyment of it when a heavy sea caught us, knocked us over, and in a moment drenched us and filled even our pockets.²⁸

²⁵ The Whitley Bay Advertising Committee, *Whitley Bay (Northumberland)* (London: Health Resorts Association, 1910), 14.

²⁶ Urry, *Tourist Gaze*, 4.

²⁷ Walter Benjamin, ‘The Paris of the Second Empire in Baudelaire,’ in *Walter Benjamin: Selected Writings, vol. 4: 1938-1940*, ed. H. Eiland and M. Jennings (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2006), 41.

²⁸ Charles Dickens, ‘Letter to Miss Hogarth,’ March 6, 1867, *The Writings of Charles Dickens, vol. 31* (Boston: Houghton Mifflin, 1894), 251. Notably, in another letter, Dickens relates that Clarkson Stanfield, the prominent nineteenth-century painter of maritime landscapes, had kept a description sent to him by Dickens of this same event under his pillow in the last days of his life. ‘Letter to Henry Chorley,’ June 2, 1867, in *ibid.*, 260.

The overwhelming spectacle of storm-tossed ships, crashing waves, and the ephemeral arc of the rainbow creates a moment of heightened aesthetic rapture. Yet, this is immediately undercut by the indiscriminate force of the sea itself, which refuses passive spectatorship. The sudden dousing serves as a reminder of the embodied reality of coastal experience, an unceremonious dissolution of boundaries – between spectator and scene, self and nature.

While early holiday guides to Whitley Bay appear to address a relatively affluent visitor, their underlying logic – the idea of the coast as a retreat from the oppressive density of the industrial city – ultimately facilitated the transformation of the seaside into a space of mass experience. This was realised in the philanthropic initiatives that sought to extend access to the coast to the urban poor, such as the Poor Children’s Holiday Association, funded by the Tyneside shipowner James Knott, which in 1891 brought 120 impoverished children to the beaches of Whitley Bay.²⁹ Here, the Victorian ethic of benevolent paternalism intersected with emerging discourses of health and moral reform, positioning the seaside as both a therapeutic landscape and an instrument of social discipline.

The rationale behind these excursions is made explicit in the correspondence of the Newcastle evangelical mission that organised the trip, its inquiries revealing a logic that is at once charitable and regulatory. Writing to a local urban official, the mission enquires:

If there is anyone in your district convalescent or feeble to whom a fortnight’s stay at the seaside would be of benefit, I shall be glad to pay for their lodgings, and, if necessary, for their board as well. Are there any street lads in your mission to whom a day at the seaside would be a treat? If so, we might organise a trip.³⁰

The seaside here becomes a space of intervention, a site where the urban poor might be physically rejuvenated but also symbolically cleansed, distanced from the corrupting forces of street life and immersed, however briefly, in a landscape that Victorian ideology framed as curative, purifying, and ennobling. By 1912, the Poor Children’s Holiday Association was providing outings for 12,000 people in a single year. The beach, initially conceived as a retreat for the privileged few, thus became the site of an uneasy reconciliation between exclusivity and mass participation, where the disciplinary gaze of philanthropic oversight shaped the early experience of working-class leisure at the shore.

As Alain Corbin has observed, with the rise of the belief in “the beneficial effects of the sea on the health of young children [...] the beach was emerging clearly as the site of extended maternity”.³¹ The shore, once a liminal space of uncertainty and peril, is thus

²⁹ Norman McCord, *North East England: An Economic and Social History* (Batsford: London, 1979), 176.

³⁰ Cited in *ibid.*, 177.

³¹ Corbin, *Lure of the Sea*, 171.

reimagined as a realm of care and protection, where the maternal order of nature aligns with the needs of bourgeois domesticity. This gendered transformation of the seaside landscape is articulated in the 1907 guide's utopian vision of a "future Whitley" where "even Blackpool might be put into the shade". "This is a dream;" the guide continues, "but it is one of the most likely to come to pass, for nature lends herself to the engineer".³² Beneath this rhetoric of harmonious mastery lies a deeper ideological claim: the alignment of the feminine with the organic, pliable, and passive, and the masculine with the force of technological intervention, the capacity to render nature productive, ordered, and ultimately subservient.

One such engineering of the coast, the construction of Whitley Bay's promenades in the late nineteenth century, signified the emergence of a new spatial order, designed to facilitate the collective consumption of the seaside landscape. The Whitley Bay Advertising Committee's 1910 guidebook enthuses:

As a grand stand from which to view the wide expanse of ever moving ocean – forcing its harmless ripples over the sand below or dashing its white crested billows in all their majestic power and beauty against the high cliffs [...] – it is unexcelled.³³

The promenade's leisurely appeal conceals its more utilitarian foundations: it rested atop a sea wall constructed to restrain the sea's destructive forces – a barrier which arrests the fluid, evolving nature of the boundary between land and sea, manifesting the engineer's mastery over nature's sovereignty. The promenade functions as a "grand stand", a metaphor that suggests a deliberate choreography of space, where the ocean's dynamism is turned into a spectacle for an audience of leisure-seekers. The implicit promise is that the visitor may partake in the pleasures of the sublime without risking the physical or existential vulnerability traditionally associated with such encounters, a spatial and aesthetic logic of the enframing and containment of nature's wildness. This reveals the fundamentally paradoxical nature of the sublime's democratisation, in which the natural escape from the modern itself leads to a domesticating movement which is in itself profoundly modern.

The late nineteenth-century carving of a swimming pool from the stone of Table Rocks – a dramatic series of rock formations descending from the cliffs to the sea – epitomises this logic. The pool was filled with sea water by the tide, and warmed by the sun. Here the sublime sea could be experienced in relative safety, enclosed in the dramatic landscape of the rocks. Nature had been enclosed, captured and made tame. This transformation of the rugged natural landscape into a site of aesthetic, embodied leisure reflects an impulse to domesticate the wild, sensory experience of the coast. By embedding human recreation within the raw material of

³² Gibson, *Illustrated Guide to Whitley Bay*, 28.

³³ Whitley Bay Advertising Committee, *Whitley Bay*, 10.

nature, the pool manifests a controlled interaction with the sublime, framed and ordered for modern consumption. To an even greater degree, this logic of enclosure is articulated by the indoor “Sea Water Baths,” opened in 1897, which, proclaims a 1909 advert, offered “Hot, Cold, [...] Russian, Spray, [and] Electric” baths.³⁴ The baths provided an environment where sea water could be enjoyed in safety and comfort. It was no longer essential to experience the health-giving qualities of sea water in the sea itself, exposed to the vagaries of the elements.

The subsequent demise of the emphasis upon the seaside as a health-giving space of nature, to be replaced by the emergence of modern forms of phantasmagorical spectacle, stimulation and pleasure is perhaps nowhere more clearly manifested than in the sea water baths’ 1910 closure: the baths were covered over, and the building became the Electric Theatre, the town’s first cinema. A local newspaper reports that year that “an old gentleman of some seventy odd years – a visitor to Whitley Bay – saw his first animated pictures the other night. His wonder was almost akin to awe so great was his astonishment at the apparent miracle.”³⁵ Modernity had arrived at the coast.

Taming the Tempest: The seaside fairground and the mechanised sublime

More emphatically modern even than the cinema, however, that year also marked the arrival in the town of that most idiosyncratically twentieth-century of coastal environments, the fairground.³⁶ In this mechanised theatre of sensation, a wealth of mechanical rides and phantasmagorical entertainments could be experienced in an enclosed, immersive sensory environment. A newspaper article’s description of Whitley Bay’s distinctively named “Spanish City” in the year of its opening mobilises a familiar trope of a modernity characterised by frenetic sensory overload: a “kaleidoscopic scene is unfolded. [...] When first presented to the eye, the medley of motion is bewildering”.³⁷ This new environment emerged as a space where modernity’s promise of excitement and spectacle could be fully embodied, offering visitors an alternative to the more tranquil, contemplative seaside experience that had once defined the town.

In *The Stars Look Down*, novelist A. J. Cronin’s 1935 account of working-class life in the industrial North East, the protagonist and his family take a holiday to Whitley Bay, a respite

³⁴ Gibson, *Illustrated Guide to Whitley Bay*, n.p.

³⁵ ‘Electric Theatre,’ *Whitley Seaside Chronicle*, June 25, 1910, n.p.

³⁶ Fittingly, the funfair was built in the aftermath of an aborted attempt to build a pier at Whitley Bay, that very nineteenth-century means of providing immersion in the maritime landscape.

³⁷ ‘Spanish City,’ *Whitley Seaside Chronicle*, July 23, 1910, n.p.

from their impoverished mining town. While the trip is largely taken up with promenades in the fresh air and relaxation on the sands, one evening's visit to the fairground and its stomach-churning mechanical rides reveals a different register of experience:

You climbed to an impossible altitude while all the panorama of the fair-ground lights lay beautiful and glittering and remote beneath. [...] And then, while you still sedately admired the view, the car poised itself upon the brink and without warning hurled into the depths below. Down, down, down you fell into an unknown, shrieking darkness. Your stomach left you, your being dissolved, you died and were reborn again in that terrible ecstatic flight.³⁸

This passage, with its vertiginous oscillation between awe and terror, crystallises the dialectic of modern leisure at the seaside – the thrilling collapse of distance, control, and bodily integrity. The ascent is one of spectacle, a moment of contemplation in which the fairground, with its glittering lights, arranges itself into a tableau of ordered pleasure, a panorama reassuring in its structured remoteness. Yet this poised sublimity is but the prelude to a rupture, an abrupt annihilation of stability as the car falls, the body is unmoored, subject no longer to the rational gaze of the spectator but to the raw intensity of acceleration, to a force that undoes the coherence of the self.

Yet this discourse of mechanically-mediated disorientation is haunted by an excess analogous to the wild sublime of nature, an echo of the sea's boundless and untameable force. Certainly, the funfair's "appeal to America, to the future and to a super-modernity" diagnosed by Tony Bennett seems perhaps to have little to do with the sublime appeal of nature which preceded it.³⁹ However, Bennett's discussion of Blackpool as a site where hegemony, ideology, and pleasure intersect is instructive here: while the fairground may appear to celebrate unbridled excess, it is in fact an enclosed space where such excess is permitted, contained, and ultimately commodified.

Indeed, the fairground offered an environment engineered to provide a controlled yet intense encounter with fear, experienced in relative safety. A 1913 prospectus describes the sensation of riding the *Rainbow Wheel* ride, then in the course of erection, as "dashing headlong into Dante's fearful Inferno amid a tumult of mechanically-produced noises and thunder, weird, unearthly, and uncanny screams, and the flames and fire of Hades (produced electrically)".⁴⁰ The description poses a deliberate conflation of the archaic and the modern, framing the ride

³⁸ A. J. Cronin, *The Stars Look Down* (London: Victor Gollancz, 1935), 553.

³⁹ Bennett, 'A Thousand and One Troubles,' 144.

⁴⁰ 'Times Law Reports, Summary of the Day's Cases,' *The Times*, July 25, 1913, 3. The report appears in the newspaper in the context of an inhabitant of Whitley Bay's complaint that the ride would cause them excessive disturbance in their nearby home.

as a theatrical descent into chaos where industrial innovation conjures the terrors of the sublime. The prospectus continues, declaring that the ride

fascinates, thrills, and exhilarates, and all the while provokes the pleasingly puzzled passengers into fits of hilarious laughter as they fail to understand and enter into the spirit of this delightful perplexity, a new sensation which is bound to become a screaming success.⁴¹

The sublime is experienced as play, as spectacle, as performance. The ride's engineered exhilaration promises an escape from the mundane through its sheer velocity and disorienting motion – yet its promise of “newness” lies in the orchestrated repetition of thrills, the spectacle of motion contained in a controlled, predictable environment. In this sense, the ride exemplifies the commodification of the sublime, where intense emotional experiences that were once tied to nature's unpredictable vastness are now staged, engineered, and packaged for mass consumption.

Claudia Bell and John Lyall, positing the commodified, mediated experience of the sublime as the defining characteristic of mass tourism, have suggested that the fairground ride constitutes what they describe as “an amalgamation of sublime landscape and the technological sublime”.⁴² This claim is taken further by Josephine Kane in what she terms the “kinaesthetic sublime”, a reference to the simultaneously visual and physical sensory experience created by the funfair, an experience which, she suggests, “represented the first attempt to commodify [the sublime] experience for the purposes of mass entertainment”.⁴³

Martin Jay, in perhaps the only text to have identified the strange resonance of this logic with the earlier thrills of the spectacle of shipwreck, examines the evolution of aesthetic experiences at the turn of the twentieth century. He traces a shift which saw “the visuality of contemplative spectatorship give way to the more tactile and kinaesthetic charge produced by disorienting motion”.⁴⁴ Jay suggests that these developments reflected a societal drive to confront and engage with the sublime and terrifying in new, visceral ways, promoting experiences more immediate and emotionally charged:

As visitors to the great world exhibitions began to grow bored with panoramas or traditional static pavilions showing the quaint customs of the exotic other, they demanded more stimulating, carnivalesque distractions, ones designed to shock

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Claudia Bell and John Lyall, *The Accelerated Sublime: Landscape, Tourism and Identity* (Westport: Praeger, 2002), 68.

⁴³ Josephine Kane, *The Architecture of Pleasure: British Amusement Parks 1900-1939* (Farnham: Ashgate, 2013), 206.

⁴⁴ Martin Jay, ‘Diving into the Wreck: Aesthetic Spectatorship at the *Fin-de-siècle*,’ *Critical Horizons* 1:1 (2000), 93-111: 101.

and dazzle. “Distractions,” let it be noted, not instructional or reflective tableaux. In such inventions as the roller coaster and loop-the-loop, a land-based version of being tossed by the stormy seas was concocted to produce a new sensation of excitement and danger.⁴⁵

These innovations, Jay claims, “broke down the barrier between spectator and at least the feeling of being in or on the verge of a wreck”.⁴⁶ The shipwreck had presented visitors to the seaside with an object of fascination precisely because it marked the collapse of control, the breaking point where technology and nature collide in spectacular failure. The funfair transformed that same pleasurable encounter with peril into something repeatable, controllable. Both hinge on the interplay between risk and safety, danger and spectatorship – in the wreck, visitors revel in their safe distance from disaster, while in the fairground, they pay for the illusion of danger that is ultimately contained. Visitors come to the fairground not merely to look but to experience – as Jay argues, this is a sublime resistant to the logic of reflective contemplation, what Walter Benjamin – who would return to the theme a number of times in his work – called the “categorical imperative of the fairground”: “those who come to gawp end up joining in”.⁴⁷

What unfolds in this experience is a reconfiguration of the experience of the sublime into a moment of modern, reproducible shock, akin to what Benjamin identified in the sensory dislocations of urban life – an ecstatic dissolution of subjectivity in the face of velocity and machine power.⁴⁸ Where once the vastness of nature – mountains, tempests, the limitless horizon of the sea – confronted the subject with its terrifying immensity, here it is the machine that delivers the ecstatic dissolution of self. In this, we glimpse the logic of a democratised sublime: the controlled terror of the fall, the annihilation and rebirth, no longer the domain of the lone wanderer atop the cliffs but an experience mass-produced, available for the price of a ticket.

In this discourse, different rides were seen to contribute to a mechanically mediated sublime experience in different ways: some, such as the *Rainbow Wheel* and the roller coaster, afforded elevated views of the surrounding landscape – temporary returns to the traditional sublime – while simultaneously enacting a controlled dissolution of the self through velocity, vertigo, and the precarious thrill of descent. Others leaned more explicitly into chaos and

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Walter Benjamin, ‘Garlanded Entrance,’ in *The Work of Art in the Age of Its Technological Reproducibility and Other Writings on Media*, ed. M. Jennings, B. Doherty and T. Levin (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2008), 62.

⁴⁸ Walter Benjamin, ‘On Some Motifs in Baudelaire,’ in *Walter Benjamin: Selected Writings, vol. 4: 1938-1940*, ed. H. Eiland and M. Jennings (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2006), 316-18.

disorientation. The *Social Whirl*, as its name suggests, was designed to simulate the breakdown of polite decorum, spinning bodies into unfamiliar proximities, converting dizziness into pleasure. The switchback railway drew on contemporary anxieties and fascinations with mechanised catastrophe, evoking the experience of the train wreck. The water slide, likewise, offered a playful rehearsal of danger: a re-creation of the storm at sea or the shipwreck, reconfigured as collective amusement. There were also rides that offered a more pastoral or romanticised variant of the sublime. *Ye Olde Mill*, for example, guided visitors through a dreamlike subterranean tunnel, its interiors painted with a sequence of idealised landscapes: Swiss mountains, tropical jungles, fairy palaces – each a stylised tableau that gestured toward an imaginary elsewhere.

Inevitably, the utopian potentialities of the fairground, the liberatory promise of the sublime's democratisation, are open to the same janus-faced problematic as that rehearsed in Bennett and Webb's contributions to seaside historiography: that the exhilarating thrill of the fairground merely serves as a momentary escape from capitalist labour, while still being rooted in its logic. This is leisure as an economy of sensation, as Bennett has argued at length, one that offers the worker a taste of chaos only to contain it, a glimpse of transgression before restoring the structures of discipline.⁴⁹ The saturnalia of the fair, for all its energy, remains a controlled inversion, a permitted wildness that, by its very ephemerality, serves to reinforce the structures it appears to defy: the sublime made accessible, but only under conditions in which its force can be safely expended before the return to Monday morning.

The fairground can be seen as a kind of "safety valve", releasing the pent-up energy of the working class through a controlled, commodified spectacle.⁵⁰ Unlike the anarchic unpredictability of nature, this "release" is structured, momentary, and ephemeral – an escape from the grind of industrial life, but only within the terms that the fairground itself sets. In the very act of mechanising sublime experience, the fairground draws on the language of liberation and release, yet reinforces the regimentation of daily existence: it is an experience of departure from the quotidian, yet one that is always tethered to it, a temporary rupture that serves to reinforce the systems that govern the individual's return. The sublime, thus, becomes something both sought after and deferred, an illusion of escape within the rigidly constructed confines of modernity's circuits.

⁴⁹ Bennett, 'Hegemony, Ideology, Pleasure'.

⁵⁰ Terry Eagleton, *Walter Benjamin, or Towards a Revolutionary Criticism* (London: New Left Books, 1981), 148.

The fairground sublime, intended to simulate catastrophe without consequence, delivers the bodily thrill of falling while guaranteeing safe return. Yet, in the story of a man injured by the Figure 8 Railway ride, the fairground reveals its latent violence:

Instead of gripping the side of the car, he was leaning forward on his stick, and in rounding the curve on the second circuit from the bottom, he was hurled out. [...] He was found to be suffering from concussion of the brain, fracture of the ribs, abrasion of one ear, and a bruise on the thigh.⁵¹

The ride, engineered to thrill and disorient, turns suddenly from a site of controlled exhilaration into one of bodily catastrophe – a body flung from the machinery of pleasure with all the impersonal force of an industrial accident. The fairground sublime, the promise of liberation through velocity and risk, operates only within the bounds of the ride’s calculated circuits – it is predicated on bodies that submit to its forces, not those that falter against them. With the slip of a grip or the tilt of a body, it could dissolve into something far more brutal. As Benjamin succinctly puts it, “what the amusement park achieves with its dodgem cars and other similar amusements is nothing but a taste of the training that the unskilled laborer undergoes in the factory”.⁵²

And yet, being attentive to the lingering presence in seaside leisure of the intractable wildness of the sea reveals a latent instability in the mass thrills of the democratised sublime. Cronin’s account of the fairground includes a vivid depiction of the milieu of the working class at leisure, whose exuberant and gaudy excesses stand in stark contrast to the earlier image of the timid miner and his wife from nineteenth-century Tynemouth:

The music cascaded, the cheap-jacks shouted, the lights flared, the crowds went round and round. All the people were common and hilarious and poor. Coalies from Tyneside, riveters from Shiphead, moulders and puddlers from Yarrow, hewers from Seghill and Hedlington and Edgeley. Caps on back of the head, mufflers streaming, fag behind the ear. [...] It was a saturnalia of the humble and the unknown and the obscure.⁵³

Here, the sublime manifests in neither quiet contemplation nor mechanised disorientation, but in the raucous energy of the crowd – not onlookers but participants, their bodies caught up in the convulsions of shared movement. The lights flare – electric, unstable, flickering in a perpetual twilight of artificial day. And through it all, the crowds move ceaselessly, swept up in the circular logics of the fair, in the rotations of the rides, in the looping repetitions of the

⁵¹ ‘Accident at Whitley,’ *Shields Daily News*, August 23, 1909, n.p.

⁵² *Ibid.*, 329.

⁵³ Cronin, *Stars Look Down*, 554.

spectacle. There is an excess here that transcends the limits of the rides' mechanised thrills, an unruly surplus of energy which threatens to exceed the spatial and sensory limits imposed by the fairground's structured experience.

Indeed, the rise of the funfair as a hallmark of mass entertainment culture provoked growing concerns about the behaviour of the masses. In 1910, while welcoming the Northumberland miners to their annual picnic, the mayor of Tynemouth expressed his satisfaction that the pitmen had chosen the more traditional resort as their destination rather than "like the giddy folk, gone to Whitley Bay".⁵⁴ The miners' presence is symbolically aligned with tradition and discipline, while Whitley Bay, with its burgeoning culture of spectacle and sensory disruption, embodies the disorienting excesses of modern leisure.

In opening the Spanish City Rotunda that same year, county Alderman Robert Mason announced that "he was not going to enter into the ethics of work versus amusement, but he would say that all work and no play made Jack a dull boy". Mason's platitude betrays a deeper ideological framework – one that situates leisure as a mere complement to work, reinforcing the perpetual cycle of labour and consumption. He continues:

Knowing what he did of the gentlemen who were directing that establishment, he felt sure that the entertainments that they would place before the public from time to time would be of a high class character and free from the slightest suspicion of vulgarity.⁵⁵

Mason's attempt to reconcile the leisure of the working class with bourgeois morality reflects the ideological labour required to police boundaries between propriety and vulgarity. Leisure is tolerated only as a recuperative for labour, but beneath this tolerance simmers a deeper fear of collective, unregulated pleasure. The spectacle of proletarian crowds at liberty from work invoked anxieties of disorder – a force too wild to be contained within the polite façades of respectable entertainment.

A 1909 letter of complaint to the local newspaper describes a group of seaside pleasure seekers as "the motley throng that clamoured around the barriers of the Spanish City during the week [...] who yelled and cat-howled as if they were not right".⁵⁶ The fairground, that temporary inversion of order, now finds itself subject to scrutiny, revulsion, and condemnation. The crowd, once part of the orchestrated pleasure of the fair, is reimagined as a cacophony of bodies and voices that transgress the acceptable boundaries of behaviour, reframed as an unchecked excess, an exuberance without restraint.

⁵⁴ Cited in Norman McCord, 'Photographs as Historical Evidence,' *The Local Historian*, 13:1 (1978), 23-36: 30.

⁵⁵ 'Opening of the Spanish City', *Whitley Seaside Chronicle*, June 25, 1910, n.p.

⁵⁶ 'Notices', *Whitley Seaside Chronicle*, April 17, 1909, n.p.

Another letter from the following year complains of “the disgraceful proceedings which are carried on night by night on a piece of vacant land [...] at the expense [of] the morals of the whole community”. This crowd, the letter’s author complains, is responsible for turning “the midnight air hideous with their unearthly yells”. Particularly disagreeable, it goes on, is the

language from the crowd, language which would have given considerable start even to Billingsgate Market. We have now in our village the well-known Pleasure Gardens, a place of beauty, if not a joy forever. [...] If such scenes were enacted and such language used inside these buildings the result would be, license [*sic*] rescinded.⁵⁷

The language of these complaints reveals the deeper anxieties at work, articulating a desire to protect the moral order and social fabric from the disruptive forces of popular culture. The invocation of Billingsgate Market – a place notorious for its coarse speech – suggests a collapse of decorum, a descent into a realm of unruly voices, of a working-class exuberance deemed too wild, too uncontrolled, too public. Thus, the seaside crowd is simultaneously a spectacle to be consumed and a danger to be contained.

Conclusion

The democratisation of the sublime begins on the shoreline, where the shipwreck, surrounded by onlookers, prefigures the rollercoaster car poised at the edge of its descent – each promising, in its own way, a glimpse of catastrophe contained. Within the fairground’s boundaries, its machinery of pleasure functions as a permitted release, an outlet for sensation and thrill. But the moment its excesses spill beyond its gates, the moment its sounds and rhythms extend into the civic night, it becomes intolerable. These letters reveal a desire to discipline the wild excesses of proletarian leisure, like the sea’s sublime wildness, to keep its disruptions enclosed within proper limits. It is fitting that the letter invokes the pastoral “village” of the busy seaside town’s past. The democratisation of the sublime thus reveals its own paradox: it is permitted, but only as a spectacle safely contained, a wildness that must never truly be wild.

Foregrounding the persistent logic of the sublime in the discourse of seaside tourism reveals a bourgeois impulse to manage, frame, and contain what is perceived as untamed. The key claim here is not that the seaside is liberatory or disciplinary, but that the very frameworks

⁵⁷ ‘Letters’, *Whitley Seaside Chronicle*, June 25, 1910, n.p.

within which we evaluate its liberatory potential have long been shaped by a desire to stabilise the unstable, to render nature – and by extension, working-class pleasure – into something legible, spectacular, and governable. The sublime, once the domain of solitary reflection, becomes recoded through modern leisure as a shared affective thrill: permitted, even encouraged, but only when domesticated and narratively enclosed. Viewed through this lens, the shift from the therapeutic to the thrilling appears less a rupture than a transformation within modernity itself – what seems at first to be an anti-modern impulse reveals itself as part of modernity’s own logic of enframing, aestheticisation, and control. The fairground thus stands at the crossroads of modernity’s competing impulses: a site where sensation is democratised, where working-class bodies are invited to partake in the ecstatic exhilaration of speed and spectacle, but only within systems designed to ensure their eventual return to discipline, to order.

In this reading, rather than a clean break between the sublime and the modern, between the carnivalesque and the hegemonic, there exists a structural continuity in how power operates at the shore – discursively, spatially, and affectively. The seaside resort reveals modernity’s capacity to absorb and neutralise both natural and social disruptions by translating them into consumable forms. And yet, in the raucous energies of the crowd, in the dazzling sensory collisions of lights and motion, something lingers – a trace of exuberance that resists complete capture. If the fairground is a machine for containing the sublime, it is also one that cannot entirely extinguish the spectre of its own excess.

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